

Geology in Motion: The Effects of Warfare on Geology

PART 3

SEDIMENT

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INTRODUCTION

Previously, we have examined the impact of warfare on geology. Part one of this series looked at examples of how bombing scarred the landscape (Laycock et al. 2024). Part two examined how deliberate flooding in warfare affected the landscape (Fletcher et al. 2024). For this final installment, we will examine the effect of warfare on the sediment itself. Examples of the effects of warfare on sediment can generally be divided into two categories: 1) Sediment creation (examples 1 and 2 below), and 2) Sediment redistribution (examples 3 and 4 below). All of these examples display how sedimentary environments are important parts of warfare, and how they can change or be manipulated in the context of the most intense varieties of human intervention.

EXAMPLE 1

Normandy Beach Sand: In August of 1942, the allies learned how difficult a seaborne invasion of Nazi occupied France would be, and how important the geologic setting of the landing location would be. An Anglo-Canadian force launched an amphibious attack on the German-occupied port of Dieppe with the objective of testing German defenses and gaining a foothold in Western Europe. The operation suffered from lack of intelligence on the beach terrains, which proved unsuitable for disembarking landing vehicles. The loose gravel on the beach caused many vehicles to bog down (Figure 1) preventing support for the infantry. The hard chert nodules also commonly got wedged in the tracks of the tanks and broke them apart, rendering the tanks immobile. As a result, 900 allied soldiers were killed, and nearly 3,000 more were either wounded or captured.

Armed with knowledge gained from Dieppe, allied geologists set out to identify beaches with better suitability to support their assault. In preparation for D-Day, the Allied forces employed various methods to obtain critical geologic and geomorphic data in enemy territory. One step included confirming the geomorphology of the beaches of Normandy via aerial photography (Morgan, 2020).

In January 1944, British divers launched from midget submarines to collect samples of the sediment just offshore of the beaches of Normandy (Morgan, 2020, Bressan 2018). Samples were then analyzed by geologists to confirm the composition of the sand, to assess the suitability for landing crafts, and ensure that vehicles wouldn't get bogged down in sticky clay-rich sediment. They observed that the sand consisted mostly of quartz, with lesser amounts of feldspar, limestone, and fragmented shells. British geologists mapped out beaches that would be ideal to support

the weight of landing crafts (Rose et al. 2006).

On D-Day, June 6, 1944, the Allied forces launched a massive amphibious assault on the beaches of Normandy. The sand provided an ideal substrate for the soldiers and adapted vehicles in addition to artificial harbors to stage their invasion. The battle was intense enough to leave behind a significant amount of shrapnel. In 1988, geologists collected a sand sample from Omaha Beach, and discovered the presence of shrapnel in the sand (McBride and Picard, 2011) (Figure 2). They identified shrapnel fragments that ranged in size from 0.06-1.0 mm in diameter (very fine sand to coarse sand), and that the grains display various degrees of roundness (McBride and Picard, 2011). Small glass beads in their sample also likely have a WWII origin, and displayed higher degrees of roundness. Their diameters ranged from 0.5 to 0.6 mm. Interestingly, the authors suggested that the glass fragments were formed in battle, not by breaking of glass,

but by melting of sediment from the extreme heat of munitions explosions (McBride and Picard, 2011). Their results suggested that up to 4% of the sand in some places consisted of both metal and glass fragments (McBride and Picard, 2011). The exact distribution of shrapnel among the D-Day beaches is not certain, but the presence of shrapnel up to 44 years after the battle is significant.

EXAMPLE 2

Depositional Remnants of Fires: Fires are a common byproduct of warfare, both indirectly through bombing, or directly through strategic burning. In ancient Asian warfare, strategic burning appears to have been commonly used in the military and was even developed into a treatise. In *The Art of War*, Sun Tzu identified 5 ways to use fire in warfare: “The first is to burn soldiers in their camp; the second is to burn stores; the third is to burn baggage trains; the fourth is to burn arsenals and magazines; the fifth is to hurl dropping fire amongst the enemy” (Tzu, 2010, originally written 5th century BCE).

Ancient fires were also caused by population growth and agricultural practices. However, by examining charcoal concentration records from deltaic sediments, Li et al. (2009) showed that periods of intensified fire frequency over the past 1500 years coincided with those periods of dynastic changes that involved warfare, often overwhelming the indicators of other contributing factors. These and similar fires produced black carbon sediment that is often preserved in lacustrine, fluvio-deltaic, and marine depositional environments. Zhang et al (2023) examined sediment cores from Tianchi Lake that represented ~6000 years of deposition. By analyzing fire-derived sediment, they found a correlation between the frequency of warfare along the Silk Road and the frequency of fires (Figure 3). Both of these studies illustrate how warfare has directly impacted sediment composition and how the sediment deposited in these catchment areas can help us interpret the past.

In modern warfare, a similar process occurred in the Gulf War in 1991, where the region suffered an environmental catastrophe. The retreating Iraqi army set fire to more than 780 oil wells in Kuwait, some of which burned for 250 days before finally being controlled (Figure 4) (Udin et al., 2021). In other instances, oil was spilling directly onto the desert floor, which mixed with the desert sand, and soot from the fires

FIGURE 1: Abandoned Daimler Dingo armoured car, along with two churchill tanks, stuck in the loose gravel during the failed Dieppe Raid. Image credit: Bundesarchiv, Bild 101I-362-2211-12 / Jörgensen / CC-BY-SA 3.0, CC BY-SA 3.0 de, <https://commons.wikimedia.org/w/index.php?curid=5411278>

Figure 2: SEM image of sand sized particles from Omaha Beach. Red chevrons indicate pieces of shrapnel or polished glass leftover from the battle. Modified from McBride and Picard (2011).

FIGURE 3: Illustration showing the correlation between warfare and soot influx in Tianchi Lake, located in NW China. The coordinates of the lake are: 43°53'29"N, 88°07'45"E. The amount of herb pollen functions as a proxy for agricultural activity. The orange bands show the major peaks of fire activity. The amount of herb pollen and population change displays an inconsistent or complex correlation with soot influx. However, the number of wars shows a strong correlation to the soot flux. Adapted from Figure 4 of Zhang et al. 2023.

FIGURE 4: A) Image of oil fires started by the Iraqi army, taken on March 2, 1991. B) Image of a bird mummified in Tarcrete. Image Credit: Aljawad - Own work, CC BY-SA 3.0, <https://commons.wikimedia.org/w/index.php?curid=6006712>. C) Google Earth image of oil contamination in the Burgan Oilfield likely caused by the environmental sabotage of the Iraqi armed forces in the Gulf War. Coordinates: 28°59'25"N, 47°56'49"E.

created a substance referred to as “tarcrete”, which at one point covered approximately 5% of Kuwait’s landmass, and is still visible today (Figure 4).

Moreover, a total of 11 million barrels of oil were spilled into the Persian Gulf, contaminating the shallow marine environment. The Massive oil fire and oil spill resulted in a significant increase in various hydrocarbons and heavy metal pollutants concentrated in the Kuwait bay and eventually settling in the Gulf marine sediment, especially within 400 km of the release sites. The sediment in the Gulf is still reported to be a highly polluted marine environment, requiring specific attention (Udin et al, 2021).

EXAMPLE 3

Alexander the Great and the Isle of Tyre:

In 332 BCE, during his campaigns against the Persians, Alexander the Great faced the formidable island city of Tyre in what is now modern Lebanon. Tyre’s offshore location, formidable navy, and impregnable city walls posed a challenge where conventional siege tactics would be ineffective. Undeterred, Alexander embarked on an audacious project: constructing a causeway across the channel to reach the island (Figure 5).

The rise of agricultural activity on the mainland in the vicinity of Tyre, including deforestation after about 3,000 years ago, accelerated the rate of sediment supply to the coast where the original island of Tyre served as a breakwater (Nir, 1996). This protected the shelf from wave erosion, resulting in a shallow proto-tombolo that sat less than 5 m below mean sea-level. Accounts from the time indicate Alexander had his engineers destroy the mainland centre of Tyre and used its timber and ruins to build a causeway exploiting the natural land bridge (Marriner et al. 2008). In the Library of History, Diodorus describes the causeway as being a kilometre-long and 80 m wide, thus allowing Alexander’s artillery and siege towers to get in range of the walls. Eventually using a naval fleet and battering rams to breach Tyre’s defenses, Alexander’s army conquered the city after many months.

The new causeway eventually created an unintended change to the natural migration of sand along the beach. The predominant direction of longshore sediment transport is from south to north, but occasional storm swells also transport sediment from the north, creating a bi-directional drift (Marriner et al. 2008, Rosen and Kit 1981, Goldsmith and Sofer, 1983) (Figures 5 and 6). Over the last 2,300 years since the siege, this sediment

movement reinforced the tombolo with at least 10 million cubic meters of sediment, mostly composed of sand from nearby beaches forming bays on either side of the causeway (Nir, 1996) (Figure 6).

This strategic use of the shallow proto-tombolo from then, without the understanding of geological processes, is one of the earliest examples of human ingenuity altering a landscape in a profound way still seen today. Today's modern city of Tyre occupies the territory of the original island city, as well as the isthmus itself, which has expanded by some 65,000 square meters and is a prominent site on the present day Lebanese coastline.

EXAMPLE 4

Sediment Redistribution as Ballast: One common aspect of warfare has been the redistribution of sediment as ballast in both marinecraft and aircraft. Sedimentologists were able to trace the origin of these ballast systems from their composition and characteristics related to their original depositional environment (Bar et al, 2019, Fournier et al, 2024). One such example was during World War II, in which Japan developed an innovative weapon known as the Fu-Go

FIGURE 5: Illustration showing the mole constructed by Alexander the Great, connecting the Isle of Tyre to what is now mainland Lebanon. This would eventually provide a barrier to sand migration, both to sediment from the south as well as the north, as indicated by the arrows in the diagram.

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FIGURE 6: A) Aerial photograph of Tyre taken in 1934. Notice how the sand accumulation is greater on the south side of the tombolo (pink arrow), as the predominant direction of longshore drift is from south to north. Additional storms occasionally transport sediment from the north (green arrow). Image adapted from Poidebard and Cayeux (1939). B) Satellite image of Tyre (yellow arrow). White arrow indicates the Litani River delivering a plume of sediment to the Mediterranean Sea, highlighting what a major sediment plume appears like in aerial photographs. Image courtesy of the Earth Science and Remote Sensing Unit, NASA Johnson Space Center.

FIGURE 8: Vials of beach sand from Ichinomiya, Japan. Image provided courtesy of the Paleontological Research Institution, Ithaca, New York.

FIGURE 7: A) Simplified illustration of the Fu-Go Balloons. Red box near the bottom shows the part of the device shown in panel B. B) Remnants of a carriage recovered from a Fu-Go Balloon on display at the Hangar Flight Museum in Calgary, Canada.

balloon bomb. The objective of these devices was to initiate widespread forest fires and cause panic among the American public. These balloon bombs were filled with hydrogen, each approximately 33 feet in diameter, designed to carry a payload of four incendiary bombs and one high-explosive anti-personnel bomb. The engineering behind these balloons was quite sophisticated for the time, incorporating an altimeter and a ballast system of sandbags to maintain altitude during their trans-Pacific journey (Figure 7).

The balloons were launched using a simple yet effective mechanism. Hydrogen gas was used to fill the balloons, providing the necessary lift. Once airborne, the balloons relied on the strong westerly winds of the jet stream to travel across the Pacific Ocean. As hydrogen leaked out, the altimeter would trigger the release of sandbags to keep the balloon at a consistent height, allowing it to be carried by the jet stream from Japan to North America. Engineers of the device designed a time-delay fuse system that would release the bombs after a predetermined period, ideally when the balloon had reached North America.

Ultimately the balloons were ineffective, failing to start any forest fires. Tragically, 6 civilians were killed by one of the bombs in Oregon, marking the only mainland deaths in the United States during the war. Despite the limited effect of the balloons, the Military Geology Unit of the US Geologic Survey was

given samples of sand recovered from the balloons' ballast system, hoping they could identify the origin of the balloons. Sand samples were recovered from balloon crash sites at Glendo Wyoming, and Holy Cross Alaska (Mikesh, 1973) (Figure 8). The task fell to a group led by Julia A. Gardner, which became known as "The Dungeon Gang" (USGS Communications and Publishing, 2024). Gardner specialized in mollusks. Other members of the group included Kathryn Lohman (specializing in foraminifera), Clarence S. Ross (specializing in mineralogy), and Kenneth Lohman (specializing in diatoms) (Mikesh 1973, McPhee 1996, and Tewksbury 2013).

Key observations of the group included the following: 1) Lack of coral fragments. 2) The sand contained over 100 species of both fossil and modern diatoms. Fossil diatoms were primarily Pliocene age. 3) The sand contained abundant mollusk fragments. 4) Foraminifera species identified in the samples aligned with those documented in Japanese geologic papers describing the eastern beaches of Honshu. 5) Siliciclastic grains were primarily of non-granitic origin, but with a unique suite of trace minerals. These included hypersthene, augite, hornblende, and garnet (Tewksbury 2013, and Rogers, no date).

The mineralogy and micropaleontology helped them identify certain beaches that were candidates for the sand collection sites,

and the lack of coral helped eliminate areas of Japan that had nearby reefs. The group narrowed on two sites on Japan's east coast, a beach at Shiogama, and Ninety-nine League Beach at Ichinomiya. Subsequently, aerial reconnaissance planes photographed the sites in 1945, and the surveys succeeded in identifying two of the three hydrogen plants responsible for the Fu-Go Balloons. These were destroyed by American B-29 bombers in April 1945 (Rogers, no date). Post-war investigations showed 2 additional launch sites further north along the coast of Honshu. Ultimately, none of the sand samples provided to the "Dungeon Gang" came from these other sites, and as such the northern sites went unidentified by the group (Rogers, no date).

CONCLUSION:

This article demonstrates the significant effect that warfare can have on sediment. In the cases of D-Day and battles along the silk road, sediment can be created and record details of the battles. In other cases sediment can be deliberately transported, such as the Fu-Go balloons and ancient marine ballast systems. Warfare can even change the sedimentary depositional systems themselves, such as the Isle of Tyre. When considered with the previous editions of this series about bombturbation and flooding, the impact that warfare has on our planet is measurable and persistent.

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